

Construction and Validation of Attitude towards Aging Scale for Pakistani Population

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 20, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: November 22, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Attitude Towards Aging;Scale Construction,Validity, Factor Structure; Reliability</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7343190</p>	<p><i>The attitude in the direction of aging can demonstrate sentimental beliefs, reactions, knowledge, and particular behavioral reactions about the elderly and aging. So far, no tool is available relative to Pakistani culture that could exclusively measure attitudes towards aging. In order to generate item pool semi-structured interviews were conducted, moreover literature review and expert opinion were also consulted. Exploratory factor analysis was carried out on a sample of 606 Pakistani adolescents and young adults. A two-factor(positive attitude & negative attitude) solution with 20-items was yielded, which accordingly accounted for 30.11% of the variance. To confirm the factor structure of Attitude towards Aging Scale, confirmatory factor analysis was carried out on 200 respondents and The Confirmatory factor analysis supported the measurement structure of Attitude towards Aging Scale retained through exploratory factor analysis. In order to ensure the convergent validity of the instrument, an independent sample of 250 participants was taken. Results provided the evidence of convergent validity as attitude towards aging appeared to be positively correlated with knowledge about aging and aging anxiety. The Cronbach alpha reliability for factors was .73 and .81. Moreover, the implications of the study along with its limitations were discussed.</i></p>

Introduction

Aging is a continuing course of living being from his birth to death that covers social, physical, spiritual, psychological, communal and mental changes (Cohen, 2002). The aging process is common to everyone and it is biological, which causes some biological changes in living species owing to these changes social disposition surrogated from being young to being old (McConatha, Schnell, Volkwein, Riley & Leach, 2003). Attitudes are the positive or negative assessment of a person or an event. These are based on past and current experiences of a person however these attitudes are changeable. It encompasses cognitive, behavioral and emotional elements, which are based on beliefs concerning the attitude entity and standards of a person (Matarese, Lommi, Pedone, Alvaro & De Marinis, 2013). When we distinguish somebody as aged, we estimate their efficiency, opinions as well as their abilities in certain areas of life because of their age (Cuddy & Fiske, 2002). People usually hold a fixed belief about social groups due to their characteristics, these are termed as stereotypes, either they can be negative or positive ideas (Baron, Byrne & Branscombe, 2003). So, the stereotypes related to aging are widespread in every culture. If these conventions are grounded on negative stereotypes towards the older population, ageism can result (Greenberg, Schimel & Martens 2002). Stereotypical stances, prejudices, and biases that aged people faced because of the older age are delineated as ageism (Butler, 1995). Greenberg, Schimel, and Martens (2002) described ageism as an unfavorable attitude or action against an individual just because of his age. Aging is facing a challenging question in this modern era, due to unavailability of intimate relationships because of the digital medium of communication where even younger generations are at risk to maintain their interpersonal relationships (Cheng, 2018). It is not possible for all members of the older community to request or enjoy physical assistance when they required (Tennant et al., 2015). Nevertheless, digital technology offers solutions to this problem of older age (Blackman et al., 2016). But Older adults have many doubts and problems with technological usage (i.e. mobile phone) (Grindrod et al., 2018), specifically their willingness and personal attitudes about aging effect the use of new technical devices (Ma, Chen, Chan & Teh, 2015). Negative stereotypes about older adults have an unwelcoming influence and are countersigned by older people of all ages in the West (Nelson, 2002). Stereotypical thinking about aging is still prevailing during this pandemic. COVID-19 intimidate to infect a notable number of the earth's population and cause their death, particularly the older adults due to their low immunity and sustainability (Koff & Williams, 2020). Commonly held negative beliefs about aging promote the stereotypes of social desolation, dependency, bodily and intellectual decline, deficiency of physical activity moreover economic burden in older adults. Due to these negative conventions, older adults are presumed negatively on several mediums like media and health care settings (Loos & Ivan, 2018; Wyman, Shiovitz-Ezra & Bengel, 2018). Levy, Kasal and Gill (2004) enlisted some

negative beliefs about aging that older adults are irritable, lonely and stubborn. All beliefs about aging are not consistently negative hence, some researches support a positive notion towards aging, according to them in old age affective experiences become more stable due to effective self-regulatory processes in old age (Roedcke, Li & Smith, 2009). As Scheibe and Moghimi (2018) found that older adults are highly amused by affective well-being at work as compared to the young adults so they possess the higher emotion-regulation capability, the evidence proclaimed that not all positive characteristics are associated with young age, some qualities are rarely associated with aging as people become more supportive, understanding and kind-hearted in old age (Steptoe, Deaton & Stone, 2015).

Some persuasive factors regarding the judgment of the older adults and aging can contribute to making a positive or negative attitude towards aging. i.e. gender, ethnicity, race, health, knowledge about aging and socioeconomic status. The sex of both the perceiver as well as the perceived has been noted as an important aspect when delineating an individual as old. Researchers suggested that females perceived men as older even at their younger chronological years than themselves, moreover, men supposed that women found older age at a minor chronological age than men (Knox, Kimuna & Zusman, 2005). Standards of aging are different for men and women as men grow in status and wealth whereas women lost their beauty and attractiveness. Age-related variations in body image and demeanor related to the aged body are more anxiety-causing to women as compared to men. Correspondingly, Clarke and Griffin (2007) claimed that females perform more actions to hide their aging and thus involve in following activities i.e. hair coloring and cosmetic surgery to compete for social invisibility. Alternatively, Bodner, Bergman and Cohen-Fridel (2012) reported males as more ageist than females. Furthermore, Gendron and Lydecker (2016) found no relationship between gender, age and attitude towards aging. To illustration, Funderburk, Damron-Rodriguez, Storms and Solomon, (2006) estimated that better knowledge can predict higher positive attitudes towards aging. In estrin families like China, females are responsible for the care of the elderly at home, so they are more knowledgeable about aging which certainly effect their attitude towards it (Yang, Xiao, Ullah & Deng, 2015). Hence, it is important to measure the attitude towards aging in Pakistan because an exploration of attitudes and reactions of the society about aging can help to formulate the educational plans as well as public policy regarding aging that can incorporate in the future of young generations for successful aging as it has been implemented in developed countries. Eradication of negative beliefs about aging could become possible among younger population via the positive information of aging, by draining those vital qualities which are considered as a basic ingredient of successful aging i.e. self-esteem, self-efficacy, self-regulation and locus of control (Donizzetti, & Petrillo, 2015), by avoiding the negative perception about aging (Nelson, 2016), consequently, youth orientation towards the mental and physical health of older adults becomes positive (Di Martino et al., 2018; Joshanloo, Capone, Petrillo & Caso, 2017).

Cultural differences in the formation of attitude towards aging

Many pieces of research illustrated that prevailing beliefs regarding aging are not alike over all cultures, indeed within countries. Age biases or negative attitude of aging is associated with cultures (Cuddy, Norton & Fiske, 2005). Shreds of evidence show that culture plays an integral role in making the attitude towards aging as Rothermund and de Paula Couto (2018) conducted their research on the sample of Germany, US and Hong Kong and concluded that HK sample perceives the old age as a period of rest in comparison to the western sample. People of old age in eastern cultures spend a tranquil life as compared to the western older population. Moreover, the Hong Kongese and western cultures revealed differences in active engagement and supporting which says that children are honored to care for their older adults. Results depicted that Indians, Malays, Pakistanis, Singaporeans, Koreans, Chinese, Sri Lankans and Japanese practice “filial responsibility”, which means that the offspring of the adults take responsibility to provide for the needs (household tasks, shopping, living arrangements, financial aid personal contact) of their aging parents, and the offspring fulfill their responsibility after marriage and even after having kids (Mehta, Tan & Joshi, 2000). Likewise, Arabs respect their older adults more as compared to the Jews (Khalaila & Litwin, 2011).

The dominant social stereotype of old age in Western culture is a negative one, as old age seems to be more widespread with negative stereotypes as compare to optimistic stereotypes, particularly in Western nations (Levy & Macdonald, 2016). Researches adhered to Western cultures generally of European origin exemplified the extensive pessimistic insight and health upshots of auto-graphic pessimistic aging stereotypes (Chrisler, Barney & Palatino, 2016). Older adults are conceived to have an undervalued status in American culture (Cuddy, Norton & Fiske, 2005). Researches illustrated that dissimilar ethnic opinions had an important role in prompting public awareness related to old age.

The measurement of Attitude towards Aging

Different instruments are present to measure attitudes towards aging all over the world. The Kogan's Attitudes towards Old People Scale (Kogan, 1961), The Aging Semantic Differential Scale (Rosencranz & McNevin, 1969), Stereotypic Age Decrement Scale (Kafer, Rakowski, Lachman & Hickey, 1980), Social Value of the Elderly Scale (Kafer, Rakowski, Lachman & Hickey, 1980), The Fraboni Scale of Ageism (Fraboni, Saltstone, & Hughes, 1990), The Attitudes to Aging Questionnaire (Laidlaw, Power & Schmidt,

2007). However, these instruments are not completely applicable to Pakistani culture due to variations in cultural, social, political, and religious backgrounds. Translated versions of these scales are not completely suitable to measure the attitude towards aging of Pakistani population because the factors affecting the attitudes of Pakistani people are different from those of other countries. Pakistani culture is a collectivist culture, respecting elders is considered an obligation for youngsters. Elders are supposed to have superior positions at their home. All previously developed scales are based on totally different cultural norms. Moreover, these few advanced measurements of attitude towards aging not specifically cover older adult's experiences, nor all cultural domains (Laidlaw, Power & Schmidt, 2007). As far as pertinent literature illustrates that there is a lack of a tool to be developed or validated in the domain of developing regions, moreover the fastidiousness of aging in these domains are not involved in the available instrument of perception and attitude towards aging, remarkably it is an immense need to construct a reliable and valid tool for Pakistani population to measure their attitude towards aging.

The current research

Due to the unavailability of an indigenous measurement of attitude towards aging for the Pakistani population, the current research aimed at constructing the reliable and valid tool for measuring the attitude towards aging for Pakistani culture which can cover all the cultural domains of Pakistan and can measure the real picture of people's perception about aging in Pakistan.

Method

Three studies were incorporated into the current research. The first study aimed at developing a scale to assess the attitude towards aging among Pakistani adolescents and young adults through a semi-structured interview, literature review, and expert opinion. The second study was intended to measure the psychometric properties of the scale, as well as the factor structure of the test was confirmed by applying confirmatory factor analysis. The purpose of the third study was to measure the convergent validity of Attitude towards Aging Scale.

Study 1: Scale development

Item generation

The 14 items were selected from the extensive literature review (Aboderin & Beard, 2015; Donizzetti, 2019; Halmdienst, Radhuber & Winter-Ebmer, 2019; Mendonça, Marques & Abrams, 2018; Ramírez & Espinosa, 2016). An additional 26 items were extracted through semi-structured interviews and expert opinion. The 40 items for the initial pool of items in the Urdu language were written for the Attitude towards Aging Scale.

Expert review

Ten experts of Sargodha University including 2 male and 2 female Assistant Professors of Psychology Department, 2 male and 2 female Assistant professors of Sociology Department, 1 male Professor of Education Department and 1 female assistant professor of Social Work Department were invited for item review and asked them to review the items critically. They determined the content and face validity of the items. Some items were rephrased, added and deleted by the experts. Finally, 40 items were retained in the item pool.

Study 2: Psychometric properties of AAS

Phase I: Initial Screening

Sample and Procedure. The first phase constituted a pilot study to ensure the psychometric properties of 40 items of Attitude towards Aging Scale and an initial picture of factor structure was obtained. The sample of the study was comprised of 120 participants, which was further divided into both males ($n = 60$) and females ($n = 60$). The age of the sample ranged from 16 to 35 years ($M_{age} = 22.20$, $SD_{age} = 4.81$). Participants were approached in different venues and Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Results. Viability of the items in the Attitude towards Aging Scale was examined through the pilot study and the final number of items for factor analysis were selected. Kolmogorov- Smirnov test of normality as approved by Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson and Tatham (2006) was carried out. Item no (4,6,7,15,17,27,35,40) was omitted due to non-normality. Lastly, 32 items were retained for further analysis.

Phase II: Exploratory Factor Analysis

Sample and Procedure. Exploratory factor analysis and psychometric properties of the scale were assured in the second phase. To assure the final structure of Attitude towards Aging Scale, the factor analysis was executed on 32 items to select the final items of the scale. To determine the internal consistency of Attitude towards Aging alpha reliabilities, the item-total correlation for scale and subscales were calculated. Gender and other demographics-based differences were also determined. Sample of the study was comprised of 606 participants, the age group of the sample was adolescents ($n = 243$) and young adults ($n = 363$) ($M_{age} = 20.86$, $SD_{age} = 4.63$), including boys ($n = 208$) and girls ($n = 398$). The data was collected by using convenient sampling techniques from different cities of Pakistan including rural ($n = 166$) and urban ($n = 444$) areas. In the third

phase, confirmatory factor analysis was implemented to confirm the factor structure of Attitude towards Aging Scale for Pakistani Population obtained through EFA.

Results

Exploratory factor analysis through principal axis factoring with oblique rotation method was carried out to explore the dimensions of attitude towards aging scale. Thirty-two items were subjected to EFA and 20 items were retained. The rest of the items had either low loadings or they cross-loaded on more than one factor. The inclusion criteria for retaining items were based on factor loadings that were either $.3$ or $>.3$, not loaded on two or more than two factors. Loading of all 20 retained items was greater than $.3$ (Coakes & Steed, 2003). A sum of 12 items that were not included has loading $<.30$ either they were scattered throughout the EFA. Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant ($\chi^2(606) = 3699.002, p = .000$). Bartlett's test of sphericity showed that the correlation matrix was significantly different from an identity matrix and the items had enough common variance that can be evaluated through factor analysis. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test indicated the sampling adequacy and its value of $\geq .7$ considered as the reflection of sampling adequacy. In the present study, the value of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin was $.85$. Finally, the communalities were $\geq .3$, which ensured that all items shared some common variance. The factor structure demonstrated that two factors had an eigenvalue of ≥ 1 . Two interpretable and well-defined factors explained 30.11% of the variance in attitude towards aging. Item 5, 13, 20, 24, 25, 29, 31, 33, 34 and 37 associated to factor 1, "Positive Attitude towards Aging" item 3, 8, 10, 14, 16, 21, 22, 24, 26 and 28, were clustered in factor 2, "Negative Attitude towards Aging".

Table 1

The Factor Loading of 20 items on Attitude towards Aging Scale for Pakistani population on two Factors (N = 606)

			Factors	
Serial no.	Items new no.	Items old no.	I PATA	II NATA
1	1	37	.65	
2	2	20	.38	
3	3	34	.40	
4	4	5	.58	
5	5	25	.36	
6	6	33	.59	
7	7	29	.68	
8	8	31	.71	
9	9	32	.64	
10	10	13	.68	
11	11	3		.37
12	12	21		.36
13	13	22		.44
14	14	26		.48
15	15	28		.48
16	16	16		.36
17	17	14		.57
18	18	8		.60
19	19	14		.62
20	20	10		.68
Eigen values			5.31	3.12
% of variance explained			18.92	11.19
Cumulative variance			18.92	30.11

Reliability

The reliability analysis indicated that the reliability coefficient of positive attitude towards aging and negative attitude towards aging was $.81$ and $.73$ respectively which demonstrates a satisfactory internal consistency (Field, 2005). The values of skewness and kurtosis for a positive attitude towards aging and negative attitude towards aging scale were less than 1 which illustrates that univariate normality was not questionable. The scale had an item reliability estimate of 1, implying the higher chances in the replicability of items over future samples (Eggert & Böggeholz, 2010).

Table 2

Mean, Standard Deviation, Alpha Reliabilities and Descriptive of Attitude towards Aging and its Subscales (N = 606)

Variables	N	M	SD	α	Range		Skewness	Kurtosis
					Potential	Actual		
PATA	606	39.2	6.35	.81	0-10	17-50	-.75	.35
NATA	606	32.3	6.32	.73	0-10	14-50	.04	-.12

Note: M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; PATA = Positive Attitude towards Aging; NATA = Negative Attitude toward Aging

Phase III Confirmatory factor analysis

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is more powerful than exploratory factor analysis (EFA) because it provides hypothetical grounds for EFA (Gorsuch, 1983). To confirm the factor structure, an independent sample (N=200), which was further divided into both men (n = 100) and women (n = 100). The age range of sample was between 16-18 of adolescents (n = 100) and 19-35 of young adults (n = 100) ($M_{age} = 20.20$, $SD_{age} = 4.48$).

The two-factor structure acquired through EFA was confirmed through CFA. It provided support for the construct validity of the newly developed scale. On the basis of initial criteria (i.e., item loading > .35), the model retrieved through EFA was investigated in CFA and this factor structure showed a good fit to the data with chi-square = 315.86, $df = 168$, CFI = .85, GFI = .90, and RMSEA = .06. Yet non-significant chi-square value is appropriate for CFA but for large samples, the chi-square will virtually always be significant, so it is sanctioned to divide the value of chi-square by degrees of freedom so that a model with chi-square/df less than three considered a good model (Hatcher, 1994). The portion of chi-square and df for the current CFA was 1.8 which epitomizes a good model fit as it is coming under the standard range. The ultimate model contains 20 items presenting a good model fit with 10 items in a positive attitude towards aging, 10 in a negative attitude towards aging sub-scale. The factor loadings ranged from .31 to .74. The findings concluded that the model was appropriate and replicable on other new samples.

Table 3

Model Fit Indices of CFA for Attitude towards Aging Scale (N = 200)

Indexes	Chi square	Df	CFI	RMSEA	GFI	TLI	RMR
Model	315.86	168	.90	.06	.90	.83	.08

Figure 1. Measurement Model for Attitude towards Aging Scale for Pakistani population (AAS). ATA=Attitude towards Aging.

Study 3: Validation of AAS

Sample and procedure

Study III was aimed to validate the Attitude towards Aging Scale. The convergent validity of the scale was ensured by overlapping constructs the knowledge about aging and aging anxiety. As in convergent validity, it is demonstrated that a scale correlates highly with other variables to whom it should be correlated (Gregory, 2004). The Facts on Aging Quiz by Palmore (1977) and revised by Wishard (2003) and Aging Anxiety Scale

(Bousfield & Hutchinson, 2010) was used to assess the convergent validity of attitude towards aging scale. The sample of the current research contained 250 participants, which was further divided into both females ($n = 125$) and males ($n = 125$). The age range of the sample was between 16-18 of adolescents ($n = 125$) and 19-35 of young adults ($n = 125$). Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

Result

Table 4

Inter Scale Correlations (N = 250)

Variables	PATA	NATA	KAA	AA
PATA	-	0.13*	0.24**	0.18**
NATA			0.30**	0.35**
KAA			-	0.27**
AA				-

Note: PATA = Positive Attitude Towards Aging; NATA = Negative Attitude Towards Aging; KAA = Knowledge About Aging and AA = Aging Anxiety * $p < .05$, ** $p < .001$

Results mentioned in Table 4 indicated that positive attitude towards aging has significant positive correlation with negative attitude towards aging ($r = 0.13$, $p < .05$), knowledge about aging ($r = 0.24$, $p < .01$) and aging anxiety ($r = 0.18$, $p < .001$). Negative attitude towards aging has significant positive correlation with knowledge about aging ($r = 0.30$, $p < .001$) and aging anxiety ($r = 0.35$, $p < .001$). Knowledge about aging has significant positive correlation with aging anxiety ($r = 0.27$, $p < .001$). Positive correlation among all scales reflected the evidence of convergent validity.

Discussion

Growing old is a passable concern among human beings, people remain usually worried about their declined abilities and it is difficult for them to accept the notion of aging (Aguerre, Bouffard & Curcio, 2008). As the aged population is increasing worldwide, it becomes vital to assess the prevalent attitudes towards aging in the community. As the construct attitude towards aging has not been explored earlier in Pakistan. The development of AAS in the present research is annexation to contemporary research in the field of gerontology, considering it has strong construct validity, reliability, and cultural aptness. Overall, the construction procedure was comprehensive and standardized, incorporating, Pilot testing of a 120 sample, EFA of a 606 sample, CFA of a 200 sample and validation of the AAS on a sample of 250. In study I forty items were selected based on literature review, expert opinion and semi-structured interview for AAS. Besides, in phase I of study 2, the viability of the items in AAS was examined in the pilot study through Kolmogorov- Smirnov test of normality as commended by Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson and Tatham (2006). Resultantly 32 items were retained for further analysis. In phase 2 construct validity applying EFA was implemented on 606 Pakistani adolescents and young adults. The findings depicted that AAS has acceptable psychometric properties. It proposed a two-factor model specifically the 10-item Positive Attitude towards Aging subscale (18.92%) and the 10-item Negative Attitude towards Aging subscale (11.9%) accounted for 30.11% of the total variance of the tool. A total of 20 items was maintained (Table 1). The satisfactory reliability of the positive attitude towards aging and negative attitude towards aging subscale was acquired that was .81 and .73 respectively which indicates satisfactory internal consistency (Field, 2005) (Table 2). Jointly, the two factors explained 30.11% of the total variances. Although the amount of explained variance was less than 50%, yet studies in social and behavioral sciences accept a relatively low value of explained variance on account of the inherited variability and vastness of many of the social and behavioral constructs. For instance, Chachamovich, Fleck, Trentini, Laidlaw and Power (2008) constructed a French translation of attitude to aging Questionnaire, they collected data from an international sample ($n = 5238$) and Brazilian sample ($n = 424$), they reported 32.74% explained variance for an international sample and the same structure explained 34.45% variance for Brazilian sample. While assessing the psychometrical properties of Attitude to Aging Questionnaire in Spanish sample Lucas- Carrasco, Laidlaw, Benito and Power (2013) demonstrated the same three-factor structure accounted for 34% variance. Empirical evidence was also present for low explained variance according to the pertinent culture of Pakistan. In their study Farooqi, Ajmal and Hasan (2014) constructed a Fear Scale with 33.16% explained variance. Moreover, Malik and Ghayas (2016) established a scale on Academic Procrastination with only 29% explained variance. Peer Pressure Assessment Scale was developed for Pakistani Adolescents with only 24.2% (Mahmood, Shujja & Atta, 2013). One more study in Pakistan revealed 28.24% explained variance in the construction of Resilience against Terrorism scale (Ilyas & Malik, 2016). These mentioned studies provide evidence for the relatively low explained variance of Attitude towards Aging Scale.

Inclusively, the existing findings elaborated that the AAS could measure the two distinct aspects of attitudes about aging and the older population while relevant to the Pakistani culture. For instance, the Pakistani community is embraced by strong moral values, decency, and appreciation for humans and regarded old age (Khan, Toor & Amjad, 2018). An international survey by Orb Media in 2018 identified the level of respect of

the elderly population in society. They collected data from 101 countries and 150,000 people participated. The results were very astonishing. According to the survey, Pakistan was on the 5th number of the list. Elder people got much respect in Pakistan which is an enduring tradition (Rendon & Terry, 2018). Thereupon, the items of AAS could manifest the traditional standards of Pakistani cultural values. Being a Muslim country youngsters must positively evaluate the older members of society. Islam pursues to impart the positive image of aging in society while establishing high self-esteem, security, and noticeable societal rapport. Islam firmly encourages to develop a healthy relationship between the community and elders. As well as the isolation and social disengagement of older adults is strongly prohibited (Bensaid & Grine, 2014). Islamic perspective emphasizes on the value system and practices. Aging has much importance in Islamic literature. According to Quran, the aging symptoms are a certain decrement in energy, delicacy, and vulnerability (Quran, 17: 23), bodily weakness along with greying of hair (Quran, 19:4), and insubstantial memory. But their decreased energies do not allow the children to start considering them useless in Sura Bani Israel verse (23) Allah almighty said clearly to be good with your parents in old age and do not speak loudly in front of them, even don't say a single word of rejection to them but do behave in a good manner. Notably, these notions do not point out bodily feebleness or weak-mindedness as the cause of seniority in Islam. The sacrifices of the older parents can be a cause of the superiority of them in Islam as they nurtured their children when they were small and was unable to do anything (Quran, 17:24) so the parents brought up their children, spare their time of youngness and bare hardships for them. This makes the older adults respectable in Islam, and all existing scales of attitude towards aging were not in line with the pertinent Islamic values regarding aging, to that end AAS is a remarkable addition in the field of gerontology in Pakistan.

In phase 3 of Study 2, CFA has carried out to cross-validate the two-factor structure of AAS on a sample of 200 Pakistani adolescents and young adults. Result depicted the factorial validity of the scale by demonstrated the acceptable model of AAS (chi-square 315.8, $df = 168$, CFI = .85, GFI = .90, RMSEA = .06). The final model contains 20 items exhibiting a good model fit with 10 items in a positive attitude towards aging, 10 in a negative attitude towards aging subscale. The factor loadings ranged from .31 to .74 (Table 3).

As the construct used in the current study was based on attitudes about aging, so in this regard, it was imperative to investigate its convergent validity with a scale which revealed positive or negative relationship with the attitude towards aging in previous researches. Aging Anxiety (Bousfield & Hutchinson, 2010) and Facts on Aging Quiz (FAQ) (Palmore, 1977) was used to establish the convergent validity of AAS. A significant positive correlation was found between the subscales of attitude towards aging (positive attitude towards aging, negative attitude towards aging), aging anxiety and knowledge about aging (Table 4). These results may arise a question that how people can hold both positive and negative attitudes at a time, this positive relationship could have been supported by a stream of research that supported the positive association of positive and negative attitudes towards aging. The latest social psychological perspective assumed multidimensional descriptions of older adults and synchronicity of both positive and negative attitudes about senior population Filippand Mayer (2005) (as cited in Coffey et al., 2015). Specifically, to the younger population, Mendonca, Marquesand Abrams (2018) reported the intensity of positive and negative attitude towards aging, results revealed that youngsters embraced a mixture of both positive and negative attitude towards aging.

However, the positive association between positive attitude towards aging and knowledge about aging was in line with the relevant literature which suggested the positive linkage among knowledge and positive attitude towards aging (Allan & Johnson, 2008). Funderburk, Rodriguez, Storms and Solomon (2006) also estimated that better knowledge can predict higher positive attitudes towards aging.

It is not merely a positive attitude, rather people's negative attitude towards aging and knowledge of aging also related to each other, the result yielded a significant positive relationship among negative attitude towards aging and knowledge about aging. Because knowledge about aging leads to amelioration of negative attitudes towards aging. Previous research with nursing students revealed the same results. The nursing students developed sufficient knowledge about aging due to frequent contact with the elderly and grip on information related to geriatric. But they rated older adults negatively due to more knowledge about older adults (Revenson, 1989) as the current study holds out the same findings. The correlational analysis also suggested a positive association with knowledge about aging and aging anxiety. These findings were confirmed by fewer previous reports (Harris & Dollinger, 2001). Knowledge about aging can cause aging anxiety among individuals because they come across the reality about aging when they get knowledge about aging. The study conducted by Ramírez, Espinosa, Dyar, Lytle and Levy (2019) yielded perhaps the same results according to the people who lived with the elderly, they become more anxious about aging and have more anxiety about aging owing to knowledge about aging. Consequently, the findings provide the evidencedirected towards the validity of AAS, proved it to be a valid and reliable scale for measuring the youngster's attitude towards aging.

Limitation

The current study entails several limitations, the convenient sampling design was used so the generalizability across populations could not be made. The sample was only comprised of students therefor this research could

not estimate the attitudes of the entire population. The scale was meant for adolescents and young adults, so the items of the test could not assess the attitudes of other age ranged people. The participants only belonged to Muslim community non-Muslims were not added in the study due to the difference in religious perspectives associated with aging. The scale should also be validated on minority groups of Pakistan and cross-culturally.

Implications

The study established the construction of the first promising tool to measure the attitude towards aging in Pakistani society. It has a significant contribution to the field of gerontology by contributing a valid and reliable scale for averaging the attitudes of adolescents and young adults regarding aging which in turn provides a basic understanding of their perception about aging so the psychologists can help them in adjusting with the aged population and learning social skills to improve their attitude towards older adults. Clinical psychologists can measure the pertaining attitudes of adolescents and young adults towards aging through this scale after knowing their attitudes they can enable the younger counterparts to survive in mainstreaming in their older age by developing the more positive attitudes towards aging. Furthermore, future researches with similar cultural contexts could use AAS.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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